

APPLICATION OF DIGITAL GAME IN TEACHING SOCIAL STUDIES FOR AN ENHANCED SOCIAL SKILLS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Digital Game is any game that is played with assistance of computer or other electronic device, online or offline. This study aimed to find out the impact of the digital game application in teaching Social Studies 7 and how it may affect the Social Skills and Academic Performance of Grade 7 students in Quezon National High School during School Year 2020 – 2021. Specifically, it sought to investigate the level of respondents' perception on the effectiveness of digital games in Social Studies; the mean achievement of the respondents on the different cognitive skills in terms of remembering, understanding, applying, analysing and evaluating; and the impact of digital games of the respondents' social skills in terms of communication skill, empathy and accountability. The study utilized a descriptive-experimental research design and a validated pre-test, post-test, and survey questionnaire were the instruments used. The respondents of the study were 53 Grade 7 students in an online class handled by the researcher of Quezon National High School where the study was conducted. The results revealed that Grade 7 students strongly agree that the digital game prepared by the teacher is clear, creative, attainable within timeframe and able to catch the interest of the respondents in teaching Social Studies lessons. Accordingly, a significant difference occurred between pre-test and post-test mean scores of the respondents showing the improvement of students' performance after utilizing digital games in teaching, except in evaluation. On the test of significant relationship, findings revealed that digital games related variables are not significantly related to students' achievement. Furthermore, correlation between the digital games related variables and the level of students' social skills, implied that there is a significant relationship between digital related variables and social skills. From the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: Except in evaluating, students' performance in pre-test and post-test are significantly different, therefore, the null hypothesis of the study was rejected. The null hypothesis of the research stating that there is no significant relationship between the digital game related variables and the academic performance of the students was accepted. There is a significant relationship between the digital game related variables in terms of clearness, creativity, timeframe and students' interest and the level of students' social skills in terms of communication, empathy and accountability. Findings rejected the null hypothesis.

Keywords: Digital Game for an Enhanced Academic Performance